

SMEs SELLING ONLINE IN EUROPE

They grew by 35.47% between 2016 and 2021

The DESI index calculates the value of small and medium-sized businesses that sell online. The calculation includes companies that make at least 1% of their turnover by selling online. The data refer to the period between 2016 and 2021 and do not include the United Kingdom.

Ranking of countries by value of SMEs that sell online. Denmark in 2021 was in first place for the value of online sales of SMEs with a value of 25.11, followed by Ireland with a value of 21.43, and Sweden with a value of 20.37. In the middle of the table there are Finland with a value of 12.14 units, Slovenia with a value of 11.55 and Romania with a value of 11.54. Greece closes the ranking with a value of 6.50, Luxembourg with a value of 6.26 and Bulgaria with an amount of 5.39.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change of SMEs selling online. Romania is in first place by value of the percentage change of SMEs that sell online with a value equal to 134.04 equal to an amount of 6.62 units, followed by Italy with an amount equal to 73.19% equal to an amount of 3.18 units and from Croatia with an amount of 59.94% equal to an amount of 7.53 units. In the middle of the table there are Poland with an amount equal to 38.92% equal to an amount of 2.49 units, followed by Latvia with a value equal to 35.08% equal to an amount of 1.94 units, and by Estonia with a value of 34.92% equal to an amount of 2.83 units. Portugal closes the ranking with a value equal to 0.54% equal to an amount of 0.07 units, France with an amount of -18.45% equal to an amount of -1.95 units and Germany with a value equal to -27.70% equal to an amount of -4.40 units. On average, the value of small and medium-sized companies that invoice at least 1% through online sales grew by an amount equal to 35.47% between 2016 and 2021.

Machine Learning and Predictions. An analysis is presented below through the use of different machine learning algorithms for prediction. The algorithms are analyzed through their ability to maximize the R-square and minimize MAE, MSE, RMSE statistical errors. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the available data while the remaining 20% was used for the actual prediction. Therefore, the following ranking of the algorithms by predictive capacity derives:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 5;
- SGD with a payoff value of 9;
- Gradient Boosting and Random Forest with a payoff value of 13;
- kNN with a payoff value of 21;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 25;
- Tree with a payoff value of 26;
- SVM with a payoff value of 32;
- Constant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it

Therefore, by applying the Linear Regression algorithm it is possible to verify that there are countries for which online sales growth is predicted and countries in which a reduction in online sales is predicted. Specifically, the countries for which online growth is predicted are the following:

- Finland with an increase from an amount of 12.14 up to a value of 16.51 or a change equal to an amount of 4.36 units equal to a value of 35.93%;
- France with a variation from an amount of 8.62 units up to a value of 11.15 units or equal to a variation of 2.54 units equal to an amount of 29.43%;
- Germany with a variation from an amount of 11.48 units up to a value of 14.77 units or equal to a value of 3.29 units equal to an amount of 28.71%; +
- Bulgaria with a variation from an amount of 5.39 units up to a value of 6.89 units or equal to a variation of 1.50 units equal to an amount of 27.87%;
- the Netherlands with a variation from an amount of 12.53 units up to a value of 15.76 units or equal to a variation of 3.23 units equal to an amount of 25.78%;
- Belgium with a variation from an amount of 16.28 units up to a value of 19.91 units or equal to a variation of 3.62 units equal to an amount of 22.25%;
- Latvia with an increase from an amount of 7.47 units up to a value of 8.61 units or equal to a variation of 1.14 units equal to an amount of 15.20%;
- Estonia with a change from an amount of 10.93 units up to a change of 12.52 units or a change equal to an amount of 1.59 units equal to an amount of 14.57%;
- Ireland with a variation from an amount of 21.43 units up to a value of 24.55 units or equal to an amount of 3.12 units equal to an amount of 14.56%;
- Greece with a variation from an amount of 6.50 units up to a value of 7.39 units or equal to a variation of an amount equal to 0.39 units equal to a value of 13.64%;
- Slovenia with a variation from an amount of 11.55 units up to a value of 12.69 units or equal to an amount of 1.13 units equal to an amount of 9.80%;
- Poland with a variation from an amount of 8.89 units up to a value of 9.57 units or equal to an amount of 0.68 units equal to an amount of 7.69%;
- Hungary with a variation from an amount of 8.92 units up to a value of 9.52 units or equal to an amount of 0.60 units equal to an amount of 6.76%;
- Luxembourg with a variation from an amount of 6.26 units up to an amount of 6.56 units or equal to an amount of 0.30 units equal to a value of 4.86%;
- Czech Republic with a variation from an amount of 19.18 units up to a value of 19.51 units or equal to an amount of 0.33 units equal to an amount of 1.74%.

However, there are also some countries for which a negative decline in online sales of SMEs is expected:

- Italy with a change from an amount of 7.52 units up to a value of 7.49 or equal to a change from an amount of -0.02 units equal to an amount of -0.33%;
- Sweden with a variation from an amount of 20.37 units up to a value of 20.20 units or equal to an amount of -0.16 units equal to a value of -0.79%;
- Austria with a variation from an amount of 14.45 units up to a value of 14.03 units or equal to a variation of -0.42 units equal to a value of -2.90%;
- Cyprus with a variation from an amount of 9.68 units up to a value of 9.09 units or equal to an amount of -0.59 units equal to an amount of -6.09%;
- Malta with a variation from an amount of 16.42 units up to a value of 14.90 units or equal to a variation of -1.52 units equal to a value of -9.23%;

- Lithuania with a variation from an amount of 18.42 units up to a value of 16.26 units or equal to a value of -2.16 units equal to an amount of -11.71%;
- Portugal with a variation from an amount of 12.61 units up to a value of 11.07 units or equal to an amount of -1.54 units equal to a value of -12.22%;
- Denmark with a variation from an amount of 25.11% up to a value of 20.32 units or equal to an amount of -4.79 units equal to a value of -19.08%;
- Spain with a change from an amount of 16.18 units up to a value of 12.77 units or equal to an amount of -3.41 units equal to a value of -21.09%;
- Slovakia with a variation from an amount of 11.06 units up to a value of 8.33 units or equal to a variation of -2.74 units equal to a value of -24.75%;
- Romania with a change from an amount of 11.54 units up to a value of 8.46 units or equal to an amount of -3.08 units equal to a value of -26.69%;
- Croatia with a variation from an amount of 20.10 units up to a value of 14.22 units or equal to a variation of -5.88 units equal to a value of 29.25%.

Conclusions. In summary, the percentage of SMEs selling online is still too low in DESI countries. On average, about 13% of European SMEs make at least 1% of their online turnover. Considering that SMEs make up 95% and, in some countries, even 98% of the companies present, it follows that the ability of European companies described by the DESI indicator to invest in online is very low. There are therefore huge possibilities that the online sales market could open up to SMEs. However, these are largely unexplored markets. Companies in DESI countries lose income, competitiveness and productivity by missing the appointment with online sales. It follows therefore, that from the point of view of orientation towards e-commerce, the premises of the fourth industrial revolution are largely disregarded for SMEs

Declarations

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